

ILM-FAN MUAMMOLARI TADQIQOTCHILAR TALQINIDA

ILM | TA'LIM | INNOVATSIYA | MAKTAB
YANGI O'ZBEKISTON | BUYUK KELAJAK
UCHINCHI RENESSANS

ANIQ
FANLAR

TABIIY
FANLAR

TIBBIYOT
FANLARI

TEXNIKA
FANLARI

IJTIMOY-GUMANITAR
FANLAR

PEDAGOGIKA
VA PSIXOLOGIYA

KONFERENSIYA QATNASHCHILARI:

- ✓ TALABALAR
- ✓ MAGISTRANTLAR
- ✓ DOKTORANTLAR
- ✓ YOSH OLIMLAR
- ✓ O'QITUVCHILAR

KONFERENSIYA YO'NALISHLARI:

- 🌿 Aniq fanlar
- 🌿 Tabiiy fanlar
- 🏥 Tibbiyot fanlari
- ⚙️ Texnika fanlari
- 👥 Ijtimoiy-gumanitar fanlar
- 🎨 San'at va madaniyat fanlari
- 🏃 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport
- 📖 Filologiya fanlari
- 📖 Pedagogika fanlari
- 🧠 Psixologiya fanlari

UCHINCHI RENESSANS

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CHARACTERIZATION OF ZINC DROSS AS A SECONDARY RAW MATERIAL FORMED DURING ZINC PRODUCTION

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Abstract: In this thesis, the elemental composition of zinc dross generated at the zinc plant of the Almalyk Mining and Metallurgical Complex was studied. The chemical and oxide compositions were analyzed by X-ray fluorescence (XRF). The results showed that the main components were 90.2 wt.% zinc. These findings confirm that zinc dross is a valuable secondary raw material rich in oxidized zinc.

Keywords: zinc, zinc dross, XRF analysis, chemical composition, zinc oxide, secondary raw material.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu tezisda Olmaliq kon-metallurgiya kombinati rux zavodida hosil bo‘lgan rux drosining elementar tarkibi o‘rganildi. Namunaning kimyoviy va oksidli tarkibi rentgen-fluoresans (XRF) usuli yordamida tahlil qilindi. Natijalar asosiy komponent 90,2 % massa ulushda rux ekanligini ko‘rsatdi. Bu rux drosining oksidlangan ruxga boy qimmatli ikkilamchi xomashyo ekanligini tasdiqlaydi.

Kalit so‘zlar: rux, rux drosi, XRF tahlili, kimyoviy tarkib, rux oksidi, ikkilamchi xomashyo.

Аннотация: В данной диссертации исследован элементный состав цинкового дросса, образующегося на цинковом заводе Алмалыкского горно-металлургического комбината. Химический и оксидный состав образца были определены методом рентгенофлуоресцентного анализа (РФА). Результаты показали, что основными компонентами являются 90,2 мас.% цинк. Это подтверждает, что цинковый дросс является ценным вторичным сырьем, богатым окисленным цинком.

Ключевые слова: цинк, цинковый дross, РФА анализ, химический состав, оксид цинка, вторичное сырье.

Problem Statement. Zinc dross generated during zinc production contains a significant amount of valuable zinc together with various impurity elements. However, due to its complex chemical and phase composition, this technogenic material is not always processed efficiently, which leads to metal losses and environmental concerns. Therefore, determining the composition and properties of zinc dross is important for developing effective recycling and metal recovery technologies [1].

Research Methodology. In this study, zinc dross obtained from the zinc plant of the Almalyk Mining and Metallurgical Complex was investigated [2]. The elemental and oxide compositions of the sample were analyzed using X-ray fluorescence (XRF) analysis. The obtained data were used to evaluate the chemical composition, oxide phases, and the presence of impurity elements in the technogenic material [3].

Obtained Results. The analysis results showed that the main components of the zinc dross were Zn (90.2 wt.%) and ZnO (93.3 wt.%). In addition, impurity elements such as Fe, Pb, Mn, Cl, and S were identified in smaller amounts. The presence of sulfur and chlorine compounds indicates the influence of technological processes during zinc production. The results confirmed that zinc dross mainly consists of oxidized zinc and represents a complex multi-component technogenic material.

Scientific Conclusion. The conducted study confirmed that zinc dross is a valuable secondary raw material with a high zinc content. The predominance of ZnO in the sample shows that the material is suitable for hydrometallurgical processing methods, including acid leaching and further zinc recovery. The obtained results can be used for improving resource-saving technologies and reducing the amount of industrial metallurgical waste.

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